

EFFECT OF ANNEALING ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR
OF SHORT FIBRE COMPOSITES WITH SEMICRYSTALLINE
POLYMER MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

The objective of our paper is to show possible effects of changes in supermolecular structure of polyamide matrix on mechanical properties of short glass fibre composite after annealing at various temperatures. The tensile strength reaches its maximum value at annealing temperatures between 145 and 200 °C. On the other hand, the notched impact strength decreases with increasing annealing temperature. Two different mechanisms of brittle fracture have been identified by scanning electron microscopy at fracture surfaces of notched bars broken by impact tests. The principal effects of annealing on mechanical behaviour of composite are consistent with changes in supermolecular structure of matrix material as revealed by X-ray scattering and DSC measurements. For example, polyamide matrix material undergoes the most intensive crystal lattice transformation at annealing temperatures, at which mechanical properties of both composite and matrix material substantially change. However, composite differs from matrix material in shape of tensile strength - and notched impact strength - - annealing temperature dependences.

KEYWORDS: Short fibre composite; Polyamide 6 matrix; Crystal perfection; Annealing; Strength; Fracture mechanism.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is generally known that additional heat treatment is an important technology applied to purposeful modification of microstructure and mechanical properties of crystalline materials and is commonly used for metals. In analogy to the metal materials, annealing of semicrystalline polymeric materials leads to the growing of crystalline areas, perfection of crystals and a change to more stable structures. Although the effects of annealing on mechanical behaviour have been reported for a variety of semicrystalline polymers, the impact on short fibre composite is not clearly understood. Injection molding produces unstable microstructures in matrix.

Naturally, the structural parameters related to fibres, i.e. fibre content, length, distribution and orientation, remain constant during annealing. In comparison with completely amorphous matrices /e.g. polyphenylenoxide, polycarbonate/, annealing of semicrystalline matrix seems to be a more complicated process. The following aspects must be taken into account:

- Change in mechanical characteristics of matrix material due to more perfect structure.
- Reduction of matrix density due to additional crystallization processes and phase transformation.
- Temperature dependent relaxation of macro- and microscopical residual stresses.
- Restriction of segmental mobility in amorphous phase as a consequence of increasing crystallinity and crystal thickness.
- Partial loss of molecular orientation.
- Possible changes in the molecular structure of matrix, e.g. creation of network.
- Escape of low molecular weight admixtures /water, monomer/.

It is to be expected that the presence of glass fibres modifies to a certain extent conditions for all above mentioned changes and also resulting effects on mechanical behaviour of composite. A contribution of other specific phenomena may appear as well, e.g. the development of transcrySTALLINE structures.

Mechanical properties and failure mechanism are supposed to be influenced by two principal factors:

- Changes in mechanical characteristics of matrix as a primary effect of newly developed microstructure.

- Change in fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion as a secondary concomitant effect.

Various semicrystalline polymer matrices differ in their ability to perfection of microstructure at higher temperatures. Therefore, the resulting effect on composite behaviour is also different. Some representative results for short glass fibre composite based on polyamide-6 matrix are presented in this paper.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Commercially available polyamide-6 Technyl C216 /Rhône-Poulenc/ has been used as a matrix for preparation of composite with 30% by weight of short glass fibres of average length 0,3 mm. Injection molded tensile test bars of thickness 4 mm were exposed to different temperatures for 24 hours and then allowed to cool very slowly to room temperature. Wide angle X-ray scattering and differential scanning calorimetry measurements were made to characterize changes in microstructure of matrix material. Mechanical properties were assessed on the basis of tensile and notched impact tests /Charpy/. Test bars for impact tests were cut from central part of tensile test specimens and provided with very sharp V-shaped notches. The radius of the notch tip was 20 μm , the depth of notch was 1,3 mm. Fracture surfaces of notched test bars were coated with Au-Pd layer and examined using scanning electron microscope /SEM/.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contrary to other injection molded composites with semicrystalline matrices /e.g. PP, PETP/, no molecular preferred orientation has been detected in polyamide matrix by means of X-ray diffraction. Consequently, the effects of texture and its possible changes at higher annealing temperatures can be avoided. But otherwise, a significant perfection of matrix microstructure occurs during annealing. Fig. 1 shows as an example two X-ray diffraction curves which document that the unstable pseudohexagonal structure prevailing in starting injection molded specimens transforms into the more perfect monoclinic one upon annealing. The most intensive transforma-

tion has been observed at annealing temperature 145 °C. Crystallinity determined by measurements of melting enthalpy increases from initial 32% to 54% after annealing at 200 °C, the crystal thickness derived from the shift of melting temperature increases at the same time from 2,6 to 5,8 nm.

Figure 1. Influence of annealing on X-ray diffraction curves of polyamide-6 matrix. Reflection technique, $\text{CrK}\alpha$ radiation.

Enhanced degree of perfection of semicrystalline matrix markedly reflects upon mechanical and especially fracture behaviour of short fibre composite. One of the most important results of our measurements was the observation that the tensile strength of composite increases with annealing temperature and reaches the maximum value at 145 °C /Fig. 2/. The strength is by 36% higher than the initial value and does not vary even up to annealing temperature 200 °C at which changes in molecular structure probably occur /specimens are getting brown/. On the other hand, behaviour of annealed matrix material is quite different /Fig. 2/. The increasing

yield strength and decreasing strain to failure of matrix material brings about a higher brittle strength of composite. Transition of matrix material to brittle behaviour with the strength approximately equal to that of original samples has a surprising response in the more significant enhancement of brittle strength of composite.

Figure 2. Tensile strength of matrix material /PA-6/ and composite as a function of the annealing temperature and ductility of matrix. Tensile tests at 23 °C.

Increasing tensile strength of composite due to annealing can be explained by the fact that the tensile strength for brittle matrix composite is higher than for the ductile matrix composite according to the theory described in /1/. The unfavourable low tensile strength of polyamide annealed at temperatures above 140 °C is eliminated, as we suppose, by special synergic behaviour of fibres and restructured semi-crystalline matrix allowing higher strain energy absorption and probably resulting in improvement of interfacial adhesion. Annealing also improves the tensile strength of composite at elevated temperatures /Fig. 3/. For example, the specimens

annealed at 110 °C exhibit a maximum percentage increase in tensile strength /38% higher than original material/ at test temperatures 70 - 100 °C /Fig.3/.

Figure 3. Influence of test temperature on composite strength.

Figure 4. Notched impact strength of matrix material and composite as a function of the annealing. Charpy tests at 23 °C.

The annealing effect on notched impact strength of matrix material is analogous to change of tensile strength but the notched impact strength of composite decreases with annealing temperature /Fig. 4/. For comparison, notched impact strength of composite with epoxy resin matrix is independent of matrix ductility /1/.

Examination of fracture surfaces by the SEM showed that there are two main regions with different fibre orientation in the specimen. A random orientation is typical for small central part whereas outer parts contain fibres well aligned in the longitudinal axis of the specimen, perpendicularly to the crack plane. The latter region is more suitable for the explanation of the fracture mechanism because the crack propagation path in the polymer matrix is clearly seen. Places in the close vicinity of notch tip were observed.

Two different failure mechanisms, both being brittle, have been ascertained. Original specimens and those annealed at lower temperatures /up to about 80 °C/ form relatively straight and smooth crack plane with fibre-matrix debonding and pulling-out fibres /Fig. 5/. Only sporadic particles of matrix are fixed to fibers.

Figure 5. SEM micrograph of the fracture surface of composite and schematic illustration of the crack growth. Original specimen.

The brittle fracture of test bars annealed at temperatures higher than 140 °C is rough, the multiple cracking runs out from the interface into the matrix and the main crack propagates through steps. Numerous broken parts of matrix are well fixed to fibres. It creates a typical morphology reminding tree-funguses /Fig. 6/. The transition fracture morphology

can be seen in Fig. 7, where the "tree-fungus" morphology starts being visible.

Figure 6. SEM micrograph of fracture surface and schematic illustration of crack growth in composite annealed at 200 °C.

Figure 7. SEM micrograph showing transition morphology of composite annealed at 100 °C. Fracture surface.

Different fracture mechanisms observed in composite are probably connected with differences in fracture mechanisms of matrix free of fibres. From SEM observation follows that great number of small, relatively stable crazes originate in the close vicinity of notch tip in polyamide annealed at lower temperatures /to about 110 °C/. High strength of matrix material and its still high ductility makes the breakdown of fibrillar structure within the crazes difficult. Therefore the debonding and pulling-out fibres prevail in composite annealed at relatively low temperatures.

Annealing at higher temperatures /145-200 °C/ results in a very brittle matrix material of low strength in which crack propagation starts immediately as one craze in front of the notch has been created. This behaviour enables that in composite the major crack easily propagates through microcracks originating along the fibres while debonding and pulling-cut fibres processes are suppressed.

Effect of annealing on mechanical behaviour of composite can be explained in terms of all aspects mentioned in the Introduction. Some recent papers concerned with polypropylene composite /2, 3/ showed that the role of morphology is not neglectable. Also the changes in molecular structure, especially in case of polyamide 6 /crosslinking, water desorption, evaporation of monomer/ can be very effective.

It follows from our observations that the annealing temperature range in which substantial changes in mechanical properties of composite occur, coincides with annealing temperatures causing the significant perfection of semicrystalline matrix. This temperature range and corresponding degree of microstructural changes can vary with molecular structure of the identical polymer. For example, the phase transformation has been completed in polyamide used in our experiments after being annealed at 145 °C while the results published in /4/ are rather different.

The ability of original, as-molded polymer matrix to changes of its semicrystalline structure by annealing seems to be of importance for the polymer-fibres synergic effect in composite. From the practical point of view, it must be considered for composite subjected to short term overheating above the temperature of long term applicability.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Annealing of short glass fibre composite based on polyamide 6 matrix enhances its tensile strength while the notched impact strength /very sharp V-shaped notch/ decreases with annealing temperature. Annealing also improves the tensile strength measured at elevated temperatures.
2. The fracture mechanism at impact tests of composite annealed at lower temperatures is different from that annealed at higher temperatures /from about 110 to 200 °C/.

3. Strong perfection of semicrystalline matrix material has been observed in the annealing range of 110-145 °C.
4. The greatest changes in mechanical properties of composite correspond to the temperature range of annealing where intensive perfection of matrix material occurs.
5. The higher degree of matrix perfection results not only in higher brittleness of matrix but also in probably stronger matrix-fibres adhesion in composite.

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BIOGRAPHY

J. Steidl graduated from the Institute of Chemical Technology Prague and joined the Department of Material Science in 1969 after being four years in industry. PhD at Faculty of Mechanical Engineering. Member of E. A. C. M.

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